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THE DECIPHERMENT OF THE DHOFARI SCRIPT –
THREE *HALḤAM* ABECEDARIES
AND THE FIRST GLIMPSES INTO THE CORPUS*

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1. Background

The Dhofari script is the conventional name for the undeciphered alphabet found in the monsoon hills of Dhofar (Zufār) and the neighboring desert regions, stretching from Oman to Yemen’s al-Mahrah governorate and Socotra.¹ In Dhofar, though the texts are mostly painted in caves, inscriptions are occasionally carved in wadi beds, on the upper stones of triliths, and on loose stones, especially in other regions. While first specimens were published in the early 20th century, the single systematic investigation of the corpus was carried out by Al-Shaḥrī and King in an unpublished report from 1993.² It establishes the existence of two script types, 1 and 2. According to the corpus known at the time, script 1 was by far the most numerous. The report provides two script tables but without attempting to identify concrete phoneme-glyph correspondences.³

While Al-Shaḥrī and King recognized that the Dhofari script belonged to the South Semitic script family and was thus related to the Ancient South Arabian and Ancient North Arabian scripts, assuming similar glyph-phoneme correspondences failed to systematically produce meaningful expressions or recognizable names.⁴ The only exception appeared to be the sequence **𐩦 𐩧** which Al-Shaḥrī and King identify as *bn* ‘son of’, identical in shape to Hismaic. This allowed them to determine that many of the inscriptions contain genealogies.⁵ While a number of scholars after Al-Shaḥrī and King have studied and attempted to interpret these texts, we were brought no closer to a demonstrable decipherment of the alphabet(s).⁶

* Acknowledgments: I thank first and foremost Dr. Silvia Lischi for the fascinating discussions on the archaeological and historical context of these inscriptions, assistance with bibliography, and sharing her encyclopedic knowledge with me on all subjects related to Oman. I thank Dr. Giuliano Castagna, Dr. Alessia Prioletta, Dr. Benjamin Suchard, Dr. Dennys Frenez, and Dr. Roman Garba for their helpful comments on earlier drafts of this paper and interesting discussions from which I benefited greatly. Editions of the Dhofari inscriptions can now be found on the OCIANA database; visit ociana.osu.edu and search dhofari in the “script” field.

¹ Macdonald 2000; Al-Shaḥrī and King (1993). The label is a bit of a misnomer as it is use extends beyond the governorate of Dhofar. For the latest overview of the field and progress on the decipherment of the script, see Castagna 2024. For a catalogue of rock art and some texts, see Fossati 2019 and also Fossati and Garba 2025 on new materials from the Duqm region. Al-Shaḥrī offered some ideas about the origin of the script in a 2000 book, which contains a number of tracings of inscriptions.

² The report is widely available on the internet.

³ An earlier script table is found in Jamme 1963. Al-Shaḥrī (2000, 84-85) provides a more extensive script table, but the phoneme-glyph correspondences are unreliable.

⁴ Castagna 2024, 84.

⁵ Al-Shaḥrī and King 1993, 34.

⁶ Again, see Castagna (2024) on the history of scholarship.

Script 1 Tables (Al-Shahrī and King 1993)

⌘	⌘	∨	∧	∩	∩	∩	∩	∩
 KMH 44								

Fig. 1 Script 1

⌘	⌘	∧	∧	∩	∩	∩	∩	⌘
 KMH 59								

Fig. 2 Script 1

 KME 42 KMD 119 KME 52 KME 32 KMD 114 KMD 116								
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Fig. 3 Script 1

 KMC 9 KMD 173 KME 3 KME 38 KMG 85 KMH 34								
--	--	--	--	--	---	--	---	--

Fig. 4 Script 1

W	X	+	H	T	1		.	X
KMA 2 KMB 6 KMC 14 KMD 106 KME 149 KMF 181 KMG 99 KMH 108 KMI 113 KMI 114 KMI 178 KMI 191 KMI 196 KMI 4	KMB 20 KMB 45 X KMB 55 KMC 3 KMD 29 KMD 192 KME 71 KME 167 KME 184 KMI 15	KMB 36 KMD 72 KME 107 KME 222 KMG 91 X KMB 33 KMC 2 KMD 180 KME 132 X KMI 38	KMB 25 KMC 31 KMD 54 KMC 55 KMD 124 KMG 140 H KMB 27 KMC 41 KMC 3 KMG 14 KMG 137	KMA 14 KME 47 KME 178 T KMB 12 KMD 60 KMG 92 T KMA 9 KMA 9 KMB 1 KMI 48	KMB 31 KMB 38 KMC 9 KME 36 KME 138 KMD 24 KMG 85 KMA 5 KMA 13 KMB 34 KMB 45 KMI 1	KMC 5 KME 138 = KMD 148 KMG 71 KMC 22 KMD 180 KMC 108 KMD 180 KMG 2	KME 108 KME 195 - KMA 23 KMD 149 KME 122 - KMB 34 KME 123 - KMG 2	KMA 6 KMB 26 KMB 45 KMB 47 KMB 52 KMD 123 KMB 126 KME 197

Fig. 5 Script 1

Anomalous Forms	«	∩	B	S	3	X	8
KME 119 KME 170 KMG 29 KMG 41 KMG 49 KMG 60	KMA 21 KMB 74 KMC 32 KMD 53 KME 28 KME 81 KME 86 KME 112 KME 113	KMA 1 KMA 25 KME 20 KME 118 KME 170 KMG 6 KMA 1 KMG 95	KMC 22 KMC 49 KMD 178 B KMD 179 KMD 180 KMG 155 KMI 5	KMB 8 KMB 75 KMD 43 KMD 163 KMD 166 KME 100 KMG 29 KMG 52 KMI 42 KMI 43 KMI 71	KMB 26 KMD 7 KMD 20 KMD 30 KMD 79 KME 37 KME 100 KME 124 KMI 15 KMI 9 KMI 9 KMI 14	KME 81 KMG 69 B KME 176	KMB 36 KMC 3 KMC 65 KMC 77 KMD 187 KME 42 KME 81 KME 85 KME 142 KMG 161

Fig. 6 Script 1

Script 2 Tables (Al-Shahrī and King 1993)

n		KPH01 3h KPH01 4 KPH01 13h KPH01 13h KPH01 33h KPH01 46h KPH01 47h
v		KPH01 18c KPH01 3 c KPH01 25c KPH01 44c KPH01 70c KPH01 19c KPH01 19h
Λ		KPH01 4 KPH01 21h KPH01 47h KPH01 1
R		KPH01 7h KPH01 12 KPH01 34h KPH01 34h KPH01 34c KPH01 34c KPH01 34c KPH01 34c
m		KPH01 7h KPH01 11h KPH01 11c KPH01 11c KPH01 11c
f		KPH01 30h KPH01 14 KPH01 14c KPH01 14c KPH01 14c
h		KPH01 2 KPH01 5c KPH01 7h KPH01 8h KPH01 8h KPH01 31h KPH01 33c KPH01 34h KPH01 40c KPH01 47h
h		KPH01 18h KPH01 18c KPH01 8 KPH01 6h KPH01 20h KPH01 21h KPH01 27h KPH01 28h KPH01 30h KPH01 30h KPH01 30h KPH01 43c
h		KPH01 1h KPH01 1c KPH01 1c KPH01 1c KPH01 1c KPH01 1c KPH01 1c KPH01 1c KPH01 1c KPH01 1c KPH01 1c
l		KPH01 3 KPH01 10 KPH01 4 KPH01 9 KPH01 19h KPH01 33h KPH01 34c KPH01 37h KPH01 43c KPH01 44h
y		KPH01 8h KPH01 9 KPH01 24h KPH01 8h
λ		KPH01 2 KPH01 3 KPH01 13h KPH01 15h KPH01 18h KPH01 19h KPH01 20h KPH01 40h KPH01 42h KPH01 44h

Fig. 7 Script 2

h		KPH01 13h KPH01 24c KPH01 41h KPH01 5 KPH01 5
m		KPH01 7 KPH01 47 KPH01 17h KPH01 27h KPH01 33h KPH01 35h KPH01 35h KPH01 11
λ		KPH01 5 KPH01 11h KPH01 15h KPH01 34h KPH01 40 KPH01 39h
o		KPH01 1 KPH01 11c KPH01 5 KPH01 5 KPH01 35c
o		KPH01 3a KPH01 5 KPH01 20h KPH01 30h KPH01 39h KPH01 41h KPH01 46h KPH01 20h KPH01 30h
o		KPH01 34b KPH01 34b KPH01 34b KPH01 35h KPH01 37c KPH01 45
o		KPH01 2 KPH01 5h KPH01 8h KPH01 14c KPH01 15c KPH01 33h KPH01 35h
o		KPH01 3h KPH01 5 KPH01 8 KPH01 23h KPH01 24h KPH01 30c
o		KPH01 4 KPH01 16h KPH01 17 KPH01 27c KPH01 23h KPH01 34h KPH01 41h
o		KPH01 2 KPH01 11h KPH01 6h KPH01 8 KPH01 22h KPH01 30h
o		KPH01 13h KPH01 3h KPH01 34c KPH01 1 KPH01 5 KPH01 34h KPH01 40h
o		KPH01 35h KPH01 47h KPH01 4c KPH01 33h KPH01 1 KPH01 1h KPH01 1h KPH01 5

Fig. 8 Script 2

o		KPH01 47 KPH01 5 KPH01 4 KPH01 1c KPH01 11c KPH01 39h KPH01 13c KPH01 29
f		KPH01 5 KPH01 12 KPH01 33h KPH01 30 KPH01 7 KPH01 20 KPH01 44c KPH01 43h KPH01 43h
T		KPH01 1 KPH01 4 KPH01 4h KPH01 14c KPH01 17c KPH01 28h KPH01 44c KPH01 44c
+		KPH01 10 KPH01 3c KPH01 16h KPH01 34h KPH01 39h KPH01 61 KPH01 12 KPH01 8h KPH01 13c
X		KPH01 44h KPH01 10 KPH01 18h KPH01 24h KPH01 26h KPH01 34c
z		KPH01 4 KPH01 12 KPH01 14 KPH01 16h KPH01 17h KPH01 22h KPH01 23h KPH01 37c
z		KPH01 15h KPH01 18h KPH01 23h KPH01 20h KPH01 32 KPH01 39h KPH01 1h KPH01 10 KPH01 15h KPH01 22h KPH01 29 KPH01 37c
M		KPH01 2h KPH01 13c KPH01 16 KPH01 30h KPH01 20h KPH01 33c KPH01 13f KPH01 34h KPH01 34c KPH01 35h
N		KPH01 5 KPH01 4h KPH01 6 KPH01 16 KPH01 5 KPH01 9 KPH01 17h KPH01 30c
z		KPH01 11h KPH01 11h KPH01 30h KPH01 37h KPH01 7 KPH01 11h KPH01 27h KPH01 44h KPH01 44h
a		KPH01 12 KPH01 26c KPH01 33f KPH01 4h KPH01 22c KPH01 27h KPH01 27h KPH01 34h KPH01 34h
M		KPH01 20h KPH01 37h KPH01 44h KPH01 44h KPH01 2 KPH01 1 KPH01 47 KPH01 5 KPH01 16 KPH01 30c

Fig. 9 Script 2

2. Rosetta Graffiti – three *halḥam* abecedaries

Abecedary KMG 120-126

Al-Shahrī and King (1993) published a panel of columns in the script 1 variant from a cave in Area G, which is situated near Ṭawī Atair in the Dhofar governorate, labelled KMG 120-126.

Fig. 1. Tracing of KMG 120-126 from Al-Shahrī and King 1993

While Al-Shahrī and King interpreted the panel to consist of seven independent inscriptions, it is remarkable that none of the glyphs repeat in the entire composition. This fact suggests to me that we are dealing with an abecedary, a glyph inventory of the Dhofari script 1. Given that the Dhofari script belongs to the South Semitic script family, it is reasonable to assume that the order follows the *halḥam* arrangement, the canonical order of which is attested in Ancient South Arabian: *h l ḥ m q w s² r b t s¹ k n ḥ ṣ s³ f[’] ‘ ḍ g d ḡ ṭ z ḍ y ṭ z*, although variant orders are attested in the North Arabian scripts as well.⁷

The original tracing of Al-Shahrī and King seems to be imprecise. I have obtained the photograph of the inscription from Michael C.A. Macdonald, courtesy of the Oxford Ancient Arabian Languages and Cultures project, and produced a new tracing below.

Interpretation

The canonical *halḥam* order is followed in the first three columns beginning from the left, KMD 120, 121, 122. However, column 4 (KMD 123) appears to break this order, beginning with the H-glyph. This is likely to be identified as *ḍ* or *z*, followed by what appears to be a deformed *ṭ*, the barbell *ḡ*, and the E glyph. This sequence would then correspond to the final four or five letters of the canonical *halḥam*: *z ḍ y ṭ z*. Column five begins with an *‘ayn*, a circle with a pupil suggesting that it still signified an ‘eye’ to the users of this script. If this is correct then the next two letters should be interpreted as *ḍ* and *g*, giving us the values of the quartered circle and the = sign, of which only one line remains visible. The following column begins with a circle, then followed by the comb which bears the value of *ḡ* in Thamudic B and then a trident with its top section effaced. If we take these to reflect the next three letters, then we

⁷ Al-Jallad and al-Manaser 2015.

Fig. 2. Photograph of KMG 120-126 (by Geraldine King, © Michael C.A. Macdonald)

Fig. 3. Tracing of KMG 120-126 (by Ahmad Al-Jallad)

have the values of *d*, *ḡ*, and *t*. Since the final sequence of the canonical alphabet occupies column 4, it is reasonable to assume that the sequence *ḥ ṣ s³ f* should have been displaced to the final column. However, KMG 126 only bears three letters. The first can be interpreted as related to the South Arabian *ḥ* while the final letter is clearly related to the North Arabian *alif*, *ʾ*, and has been recognized as such since Al-Shaḥrī and King (1993). This leaves the half circle with the value of either *s³*, *ṣ*, or *f*. I suggest we should interpret it as a *f* based on similarly shaped glyphs in other South Semitic scripts. This value will be demonstrated below.

Abecedary KMD 28-31

Al-Shaḥrī and King’s corpus contains another hitherto unidentified *halḥam* abecedary from Area D, between the Wadi Arzat and Medinat al-Ḥaq roads. This one comprises only three columns, KMD 28-30, which were originally interpreted as separate inscriptions.

Fig. 4. Tracing of KMD 28-31 by King (1993)

Fig. 5. Photo of KMD 28-31 (by Geraldine King, © Michael C.A. Macdonald)

Michael C.A. Macdonald has kindly provided the photo of this panel. The original tracing is quite accurate but there are some points that can be improved. A new tracing is provided below.

If we take our understanding of the KMG 120-126 abecedary, then column KMD 30 can be interpreted as follows: *h l ḥ m q w s² r b t s¹ k n g ḡ t {k} {ḡ} {r} {t}*. The first thirteen

Fig. 6. Tracing of KMD 28-30 (by Ahmad Al-Jallad).

letters follow the correct order but then the author jumps to *g*, skipping the sequence $h\ s^3\ f$ $\acute{\text{d}}\ g$, and then skips *d* to reach \acute{g} and *t*. The section following this is extremely difficult to interpret. The glyph Y could be taken as a *h* or a *k* but its position here is unexpected. It is followed by what appears to be a \acute{g} and then a dot and a cross. Perhaps the comb-like glyph here should be understood as an $\acute{\text{r}}$, which is missing in KMD 30, followed by the $\acute{\text{c}}$. Realizing his errors, the author adds a column to the left (KMD 29) that attempts to supply the missing sequences. The first three letters read $d\ \acute{g}\ t$, rectifying the missing *d* of KMD 30. Following this, he repeats $s^l\ k\ n$ and then supplies the missing $\acute{\text{d}}\ g$. Finally, in the left-most column, KMD 28, the author provides the final sequence of the alphabet to correct the confused arrangement of glyphs in KMD 30. These read: $d/z\ y\ t\ z$. When putting all columns together, we produce an alphabet very similar to KMG 120-126, only lacking the sequence $h\ f\ \acute{\text{r}}$.

The Duqm-Nafun abecedar

In 2025, Garba et al. published a report on the Czech archaeological expedition ARDUQ 2022-2023 field season at Duqm, east of Dhofar, in the Omani journal *Athar – Bulletin of Archaeological Research in the Sultanate of Oman*.⁸ The report included an investigation of

⁸ The text was also presented in a published poster by Garba et al. 2022. This text, along with other rock art in Nafun, was documented by the Czech archaeological expedition ARDUQ (Archaeological Landscape and Environmental Dynamics of Duqm and Nejd) in Oman, led by R. Garba, with tracings carried out by Angelo E. Fossati, and funded by Praemium Academiae of the Czech Academy of Sciences.

rock art and provided a figure (#2) by Angelo E. Fossati illustrating the chronological development of styles and inscriptions. One of the illustrations contained a tracing by Fossati of a long Dhofari-script inscription divided into seven sections by word dividers. I have produced the following tracing based on the tracing of Fossati, interpreted in light of the Dhofari abecedaries studied above.

Fig. 7. Tracing of the *Duqm-Nafūn* abecedary
(by Ahmad Al-Jallad based on the tracing of Fossati in Garba et al. 2025, Figure 2)

In light of the previously discussed texts, it is clear that the present inscription is an abecedary and that it contains nearly identical letter shapes. I offer the following reading based on the etymological values of the glyph shapes. The letter sequences are separated by word dividers in groups of 5, 5, 3, 3, 3, 3, 4.

h l ḥ m q / w s² r b t / s¹ k n / f ḥ^ʿ / ʿ d g / d ḡ ṭ / z y ṭ z

Commentary

Unlike the abecedaries from Dhofar, the *Duqm-Nafūn* version more closely follows the canonical order. The sequence *z-d y ṭ z* is placed in final position as opposed to KMG 120-126, where it occupies column 4. However, the sequence *f ḥ^ʿ* appears to have exchanged the canonical positions of *f* and *ḥ*, if the current interpretation is correct. The single glyph before *y* takes the shape of an X rather than a H as found in the Dhofari abecedaries.

3. Synthesis

The three abecedaries exhibit an inventory of 26 glyphs. Conspicuously missing are distinctions between *z* and *ṣ*, *ṭ* and *s³*, and *d* and *z*. This would suggest that the interdental and sibilants have merged, and that the glyphs used to represent the etymological interdentals *ṭ* and *z* came to signify the outcome of these mergers. The case of *d* and *z* is more complicated. The final sequence in both the Dhofari alphabets and that of *Duqm-Nafūn* contain only one glyph in the position of *d-z*, but in the latter, the sign is an X, which is similar to the glyph signifying *z* in Himaitic, while it is a H in Dhofari, similar to the *d* glyph of Thamudic B and other North Arabian scripts.⁹ The merger of the sibilants and interdentals is a feature of Ḥasaitic, an eastern Arabian language carved along the Gulf.¹⁰ Ḥaḍramitic also attests this merger, so we could be dealing with an ancient, areal sound change of east Arabia, extending from Ḥaḍramut across Oman and along the Gulf northwards.¹¹

⁹ See Macdonald 2000, 34.

¹⁰ On the phonology of Hasaitic, see Al-Jallad 2024.

¹¹ The status of the interdentals is unclear in Qaṭrayith, the vernacular of the gulf region in the early Islamic period (Al-Jallad 2025b).

Chart 1: The Dhofari alphabets in context with other attested South Semitic abecedaries

	KMG 120-126	KMD 28-31	Duqm- Nafūn	Thamudic B ¹²	South Arabian	Dadanitic (JSLih 152) ¹³
<i>h</i>						
<i>l</i>						
<i>ḥ</i>						
<i>m</i>						
<i>q</i>						
<i>w</i>						
<i>s²</i>						
<i>r</i>						
<i>b</i>						
<i>t</i>						
<i>s¹</i>						
<i>k</i>						
<i>n</i>						
<i>ḥ</i>		NA				
<i>š > z̄</i>						
<i>s³ > t̄</i>						
<i>f</i>		NA				

¹² Al-Jallad and al-Manaser 2015.¹³ <https://ociana.osu.edu/inscriptions/14076>.

	KMG 120-126	KMD 28-31	Duqm- Nafūn	Thamudic B	South Arabian	Dadanitic (JSLih 152)
·		NA				
·						
<i>d</i>						
<i>g</i>						
<i>d</i>						
<i>ḡ</i>						
<i>t</i>						
<i>z</i>		> <i>d</i>				
<i>d</i>			> <i>z</i>			
<i>y</i>						
<i>t <> s³</i>						
<i>z <> ṣ</i>						

3.1 Commentary on the letter shapes

Many of the letter shapes are unremarkable from the point of view of the South Semitic script archetype. The following commentary will concern glyphs that inform our understanding of the history of the script and its unique features.

: The two-horned *alif* sides is more closely related to the North Arabian scripts; this shape is encountered in Taymanitic, Dadanitic, Thamudic B, and occasionally in Thamudic C. The Ancient South Arabian form of the *alif* is simplified to an open rectangle with a bolt extending from its top.

: With the *dāl* taking a new shape, the loop of the original *q* seems to have simplified in some cases to a half loop resembling the *d* of other scripts. The original form consisting of a circle with an intersecting vertical line is still sometimes encountered.

⤿: The s^2 takes this form in many South Semitic scripts; however, a variant is attested with a loop at one end that can be only read as an s^2 , , which has two ears.

Fig. 8. KMC 3

●: The dot was read by Al-Shahrī and King (1191) as an n but its position in the abecary clearly indicates that it signifies an r .

┆: The n has been simplified to a dash from the original bolt shape preserved in Ancient South Arabian and several North Arabian scripts. This form seems to have developed in several scripts independently, including Safaitic, Thamudic B, and occasionally Himaic.

⤿: This glyph is close in form to the South Arabian and Himaic h .¹⁶

⤿: The f has a tight U-shape, a glyph identified in Thamudic D but with an unidentified value.¹⁷ This shape is already approximated in Dadanitic and appears to be a simplification of a Thamudic B variant, .¹⁸

⊕: The quartered circle is encountered across many scripts but never with the value $ḡ$. Perhaps this can be regarded as a development from the # glyph attested in Ancient North Arabian scripts, such as Safaitic and Thamudic B. One cannot exclude a relationship with the Himaic concentric circles. The #-glyph appears in some inscriptions from Dhofar and may be ancestral to the form encountered here.

||: The parallel lines for the g have no correlates in other South Semitic scripts.

¹⁴ The name ls^2ms^l is attested 29 times in Safaitic (OCIANA, consulted 19/6/2025).

¹⁵ On the Himaic script, see Robin and Gorea 2016.

¹⁶ On the definition of this category, see Macdonald 2000.

¹⁷ Al-Jallad 2025a.

¹⁸ On Dadanitic, see Kootstra 2022.

 with the subsequent loss of the shaft.

 : This is the attested shape of the *g* in Thamudic B.¹⁹

 : The *z* does not have this shape in other scripts, but a similar form is attested in Himaitic signifying the *d*. It is likely that the KMG 120-126 trident originally shared the same form, though its upper tines are now worn away.

 : The *z* of the Duqm abecedary has the same shape as the Himaitic *z*, perhaps a simplification of the battle axe glyph attested in Ancient South Arabian.

 : The *d* glyph in Dhofari abecedaries, which likely represents the *z* sound, shares its common North Arabian shape with those found in Taymanitic, Thamudic B, and D, as well as a variant in Dadanitic. This distinguishes it from the South Arabian # glyph.

 : The final glyph sits in the position of *z* but likely signifies *ṣ* phonetically. This phoneme is not yet attested in Thamudic B or Himaitic, and the shape is unique among those known in the South Semitic scripts.

Let me make one more important observation. The Duqm-Nafūn uses word dividers to separate sequences of letters into blocks. They are divided as such:

hlḥmq / ws²rbt / s¹kn / flḥ' / 'dḡ / dḡt / zy(t-s³)(ṣ-z)

While KMG 120-126 does not employ word dividers, the alphabet is spread across individual columns that correspond to the exact same segments as the Duqm-Nafūn abecedary, even though segment four and seven have been exchanged in the latter. This speaks to the existence of a shared mnemonic clustering the letters together to form pronounceable pseudo-word, like the Arabic *'abjad-hawwaz* mnemonic.

120 *hlḥmq*
 121 *ws²rbt*
 122 *s¹kn*
 123 *z-dytz*
 124 *'dḡ*
 125 *dḡt*
 126 *flḥ'*

3.2 Origin of the Dhofari Script 1

The close examination of the Dhofari letter shapes suggests a resemblance to North Arabian and specifically Thamudic B, with the following glyph shapes constituting important isoglosses: *'*, *ḡ*, *d*, *s²*, and *n*. The *f* is also best explained from a Thamudic B or Dadanitic archetype. In total, almost all diagnostic letters side with their North Arabian forms against South Arabian. The *alif*, for example, can only have developed from a shape bearing the two 'horns' of the Proto-Sinaitic archetype, preserved in a number of North Arabian scripts, rather

¹⁹ See the script chart in Macdonald 2000.

than the evolved one-horned Ancient South Arabian form.²⁰ Only the letter *h* can be plausibly attributed to South Arabian origins; however, a North Arabian parallel can also be found. Thus, we can carefully suggest that the Dhofari script developed from a North Arabian archetype, which underwent significant local modification.

4. Concluding remarks and directions

This paper has provided the decipherment for Script 1 of the Dhofari alphabet. Further work is necessary to unravel the phoneme-glyph values of Script 2, which impressionistically appears to be closer to South Arabian. During the course of this study, however, it is clear that Script 1 also exhibits several paleographic phases. This much is demonstrated by the two shapes of the *s*² glyph. However, a number of inscriptions exhibit letter shapes, while related to the script discussed in this paper, also exhibit forms not attested in the abecedaries. These are: the horizontal line, , and several other shapes that do not appear in the abecedaries that King identified as ‘anomalous.’²¹ These anomalous forms also tend to appear in the same inscriptions, suggesting that they form a discrete script type. See for example:

Fig. 9. KME 32

I would therefore suggest labelling the script of the abecedaries discussed herein *Script 1a*. There are clearly different yet related sub-scripts in this category, which can be labelled *1b*, *1c*, etc. as the variation is sorted out when more texts become available.

The decipherment of Script 1a has also revealed that the main obstacle preventing a linguistic connection with the Modern South Arabian languages, the word *bn*, has been overcome. The word ‘son’ is in fact correctly read as *br*, which is compatible with the Modern South Arabian languages. What is not compatible, however, is the loss of interdentals, a feature

²⁰ On the significance of the shape of the *alif* for understanding the development of the South Semitic scripts, see Al-Jallad 2025c.

²¹ Al-Shahrī and King 1991, fig. 6.

preserved throughout the language family.²² The language expressed by Script 1a while probably related to Mehri, Jibbali, Socotri, and Harsusi cannot be directly ancestral to any of these modern languages. Their ancient antecedent, however, may lie hidden behind one of the other variant script types.

Appendix: Remarks on a few published texts

1. *Edition of Selected Texts from Al-Shahrī and King 1993*

The following texts were selected from Al-Shahrī and King's edition based on their contents and the quality of the copies. These texts demonstrate the validity of the decipherment and provide our first glimpse into the pre-Islamic language and culture of Dhofar. This edition is extremely preliminary. While the readings are more or less secure, the interpretation of the inscriptions is dependent upon building up a critical mass of parallels to establish formulaic expressions and arbitrate between competing interpretations. This is only partially accomplished here.

Area D

KMD 50

{h}wg ... hbyt

Commentary: The *h* is uncertain. The formula *hwg(t)* is recurring and may reflect a common formula expressing need or yearning, similar perhaps to the *ts²wq* formula attested in Ancient North Arabian.²³ *Hbyt* could be a personal name derived from the C-stem of *byt* 'to spend the night' or a noun with the *h* definite article meaning 'the encampment.'

²² See, for example, Rubin 2018. For an overview of all the languages, see Simeone-Senelle 2011.

²³ On this verb, see SafDict, 15.

KMD 51-52

51: *yhqh l-rs'*

52: *hhy*

'grant life'

Commentary: It is unclear if these constitute a single text. It is possible to understand *yhqh* as a prefix conjugated C-stem verb of *wqh* 'to obey' with *rs'* as its object introduced by the dative preposition *l-*. KMD 52 reads unambiguously as a C-stem verb of *hyw* 'to give life'.

KMD 54

hgf-h

'help him!'

Commentary: This is the C-stem ultimately from the root *gwt* meaning 'to help' with a *-h* suffixed pronoun. The spelling with *f* suggests that the language underwent the sound change *t > f* in this root, which sporadically happens in Arabic. This recalls the Quranic word *fūm* 'garlic' for Semitic *tūm*. The opposite happens in some modern Arabic dialects, where Old Arabic *fum* 'mouth' becomes *tum*.

KMD 94

mḥmd

Commentary: It is unclear if this is simply a name or a statement of praise, as the root *ḥmd* is used quite commonly in formulaic expressions.

KMD 188

ḥyb br mys^l

Commentary: *ḥyb* is an attested name in Ancient North Arabia and *mys^l* reflects a known root and is also previously attested.²⁴

Area E

KME 60-62

²⁴ OCIANA, consulted 21 June, 2025.

62: *ḥmd--- ḥmdt k-mḥy br n---*

‘Great praise be to Mḥy son of N---’

Commentary: The repetition of the *ḥmd* sequence may reflect an infinitive absolute construction where the first *ḥmd* is an imperative or passive verb while the second is the infinitive. *K-* could be taken as the preposition ‘to’ as in Minaic. *Mḥy* is a known name, compare with Arabic *muḥyī*. The name of the father is missing.

ḥmdt k- mḥ{y}

‘praise be to {Mḥy}’

Commentary: See KME 62. The final *y* is restored on the basis of the previous inscription.

{m} byt ḥm ṛ l-yḡf rmt

Commentary: This text is extremely complicated and we will need more concrete parallels to sort out its meaning. The first uncertain *m* could be an indefinite pronoun introducing a relative clause. Then *byt* ‘to encamp’ as we have discussed before. The letters *ḥm* could reflect the verb ‘to protect’, Arabic *ḥamā*, *iḥmi*. The next two letters, *ṛ*, are difficult to interpret. These are followed by *l-*, the preposition *al-*. Following that is the divine name *yḡf* perhaps */yaḡūf/*, derived from *yaḡūt*, but its role in the clause is uncertain. *Rmt* could be a place name; etymologically it appears to be connected to the root *rVm* ‘high.’ The element *ṛ*

does not lend itself to a straightforward interpretation in the present context. It is tempting to connect it with the MSAL ablative preposition *ar*,²⁵ but the compounding of two prepositions would be odd, although not unprecedented.

Fig. 10. KME 68-69 (Photo Geraldine King, © Michael C.A. Macdonald)

KME 68-69

68: *l ḥwdb*

69: *br kwtr*

Commentary: This is a short genealogy introduced by the *lam auctoris*. I have interpreted the dotted circle as a *d*, which is an attested variant of the letter. The name *kwtr* corresponds to Quranic *kawtar* and Ugaritic *kōtaru-wa-ḥasisu*.

n'rt

Commentary: A female name, cognate with Hebrew נַעֲרָה 'girl.'

²⁵ I thank G. Castagna for recognizing this possible cognate.

KME 139

ḥwg ʿmrn w ʿ{n}

‘ʿmrn was in need and suffered’

Commentary: The name *ʿmrn* corresponds to Arabic *ʿimrān* and is common across Ancient North Arabia. *Ḥwg* seems to be a common formula expressing need or yearning, similar perhaps to the *ts²wq* formula attested in Ancient North Arabian. The final two letters *ʿn* may reflect the verb *ʿanā* ‘to suffer’, a common expression also in longing texts.

KME 143-144

144: *w gml bʿd ḥ---* ‘and a camel on the behalf of ----’

Commentary: This corresponds to the common rock art genre, where drawings are signed by their authors. The word *bʿd* probably corresponds not to Classical Arabic *baʿda* after but the sense found in Hebrew and Safaitic, namely, ‘on account of.’²⁶

²⁶ SafDict, 58.

KME 152

hwgt gbnt
 'Gbnt was in need'

Commentary: The term *hwgt* would seem to inflect for gender, exhibiting the feminine form here in agreement with *gbnt*, who is presumably a female. The masculine name *gbn* is attested 10 times in Safaitic.²⁷

KME 166

nḥmd ḥy l w ybq b-ḥy ḥmd
 'we praise/let us praise greatly ḥy/ and may he remain alive'

²⁷ OCIANA, consulted 21 June, 2025.

Commentary: *nhmd* is the first-person prefix conjugated verb, which is usually plural in most Semitic languages but can signify the singular in Western Arabic dialects and Soqotri.²⁸ *yl* is possibly a personal name. *ybq* corresponds to Arabic *yabqa* ‘(let him) remain’ *b-* ‘in’ and *hy* ‘living’. The final *hmd* should be construed as an infinitive absolute, amplifying the main verb.

KME 191

s²b¹t hg w tbb d---

‘S²b¹t was in need/went on a pilgrimage and suffered loss ---’

Commentary: The verb *hg* could be a simplified form of *hwg* ‘to need’ which would nicely match *tbb* ‘to suffer loss’.²⁹ However, one cannot rule out understanding it as a reflex of *hgg* ‘to make a pilgrimage’.

Area G

KMG 22-25

²⁸ P.c. Leonid Kogan.

²⁹ Compare with Classical Arabic *tabba* ‘to suffer a loss’ (Lane 1863-1893, 293a).

22: *m---*

23: *w 'l-h yd s'mh*

24: *s'll*

25: *'hwg*

'S'll was in need' so may the hand of S'mh be upon him'

Commentary: This remarkable text contains a prayer to a deity *s'mh*, previously attested only in the Dumaitic inscriptions as *bsmh*,³⁰ but can perhaps be connected to the theophoric element in the name *sumhuram* 'sumhu (his name) is high.' S'll is likely a personal name. The interpretation of the form *'hwg* is unclear but it is clearly related to *hwg* and *hwgt*.

Area H

KMH 9-10

9: *k-s²ms'*

10: *md hq*

Commentary:

md: This should be understood as the suffix conjugated verb *madda* 'to extend', compare with Mehri *məd* 'to stretch out'. In the C-stem, it means 'to give'.

hq: The subject of the verb *md*. This personal name is not attested in ANA, but the root is productive in Arabic where it means 'to crush, break' (Lane, 2896a).

k-: This is the dative preposition, also attested in Minaic. In Mehri, the *k-* preposition serves a number of functions, but a dative sense can still be detected in its use in 'have' constructions, *šəh* 'he has' < *ka-hu 'to him'.

s²ms': The pan-Semitic solar deity.

³⁰ Norris 2018.

Area I

KMI 6-7

7: *nmml br s²hm*6: *nbrt hyw-hn*‘Nmml son of S²hm; may life be elevated’

Commentary: *nbrt* is perhaps the optative suffix conjugation of *nabara* ‘to elevate, raise’. *Hywhn* might be constructed as the word life *hyw* with the suffixed definite article *-hn* on a singular, as in Ḥaḍramitic.

KMH 5

ymg{d} rb b-ymm

‘The lord who is in Ymm is glorious’

Commentary: This interpretation is extremely speculative. *Ymgd*, if the *d* is correctly read, could be the prefix conjugated verb, *yamgudu* ‘to be glorious’. *Rb* is *rabb* lord. *B-* is taken as a locative preposition, which leaves us with *ymm*, perhaps cognate with *yamāmah* an area in central Arabia. The term *rb* is not explicitly marked as definite, which could mean it either includes a vocalic definite article or lacks an article entirely.

Area J

KMJ 20-22

20: *ḥws* ----

21: *yhmm*

22: *tymhn br s'ybs'*

'Tymhn son of Sybs was mindful in a state of *ḥws'*

Commentary: Tymhn is a name with a post-positive definite article *-hn* as in Ḥaḍramitic. S'ybs' is an odd name and its etymology is not immediately apparent to me. Perhaps it is Greek, Sabeos. Yhmm is the prefix conjugation of 'to worry', 'to think about' *hmm*, and here should perhaps be compared to the *dkr* 'to be mindful of' formula in some Ancient North Arabian and Nabataean inscriptions. Ḥws' reoccurs so it is unlikely to be a personal name. Perhaps it is an adverb but its meaning is not clear at the current moment.

KMJ 82-83

82: $s^l w^c$

83: $br ny^t ht$

Commentary: The name $S^l w^c$ corresponds to the Noahic idol mentioned in Quran 71:23, $suwā^c$. The etymology of the name $ny^t ht$ is not clear.

Re-reading of the Jebel Qamar painted inscriptions

We will attempt an interpretation of the panel of painted inscriptions from Jebel Qamar, Oman.³¹

Fig. 11. Jebel Qamar painted inscriptions, Le quellec et al. 2018

Columns read from right to left

1. $\dot{s}wb^l$

2. $\dot{h}g br \dot{h}bd$

3. $\dot{h}ws^l$

4. $br br s^3(<t>)^c dn$

5. $w zhr b-\dot{h}wg s^2ms^l$

6. $\dot{h}yw$

7. $^hmm l-gwhl$

1. If the \dot{s} is read correctly and is a variant of the \dot{z} -glyph, this would produce the name $\dot{s}wb^l$, with an il -theophoric element. The root $\dot{s}wb$ signifies ‘pouring forth’ (Lane 1863-1893, 1739c), likely in this case a reference to precipitation. The name can therefore be compared to the common North Arabian theophoric compound $\dot{g}(w)\dot{t}^l$ ‘It has provided rain’.

³¹ Le Quellec et al. 2018. I thank Giuliano Castagna for sharing the correct location.

2. *hg* son of *hbd*: The name *hg* ‘pilgrimage’ or ‘feast’ is common; however, *hbd* is unattested but recurring.³²
3. *Hws^l* reoccurs so it seems to be a formulaic expression. There is a painted line before the *h* slightly to the left, but this may not be an intentional mark. If it is correct, then it reads *nhws^l*.
4. *br* son of *s³dn* are both common and unremarkable names.³³ Noteworthy, however, is the use of the barbel to transcribe etymological *s³*, confirming the foregone discussion on the sibilants.
5. The name *zhr* would correspond with Arabic *zuhayr* and is followed by the preposition *b*-‘in’ and *hwg* as from the root ‘to need’ with the pan-Semitic solar deity, Shams, as the object.³⁴ One can plausibly read this section as ‘and/with Zhr, and he was in need of Shams.’
6. This word is clearly derived from ‘life,’ but it is not possible to know if it is a verb or noun or its relationship with the column to its left. For now, I have taken it as a personal name and the subject of the verb in column 7.
7. The sequence *hmm* is difficult. The root *hmm* reoccurs in the inscriptions and appears to be a formulaic expression, discussed in KMG 21, meaning ‘to worry about’ or ‘to be mindful of.’ The final element, *gwhl*, is probably a name, which in Mehri means ‘poet’.³⁵ If we take line 6 as belonging to this sequence then it could be an expression of longing or worrying by a man called *hyw* for another called *gwhl*, an extremely well-attested genre in the Ancient North Arabian graffiti.

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³² *hg* is attested at present some 215 times in OCIANA (accessed 5 June, 2025).

³³ *s³dn* is attested 21 times in OCIANA (accessed 5 June, 2025) whereas the name *br* is attested 21 times.

³⁴ The deity *shams* was especially popular in East Arabia, see Robin and Priolella 2013.³⁴ Johnstone 1987, 116.

³⁵ Johnstone 1987, 116.

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